

TRENDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF DEVELOPER SERVICES IN THE INVESTMENT AND CONSTRUCTION SECTOR

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Abstract. *This article explores the distinctive features and prospects of developing developer services in the construction sector, focusing on contemporary economic, technological, and ecological challenges. Key trends such as the increasing interest in "green construction," the implementation of digital technologies, and the evolving approaches to urban environment design are examined. The primary issues identified include the sector's insufficient adaptation to legislative changes, a shortage of qualified personnel, and difficulties in attracting investments. Particular attention is given to innovative development opportunities, particularly the application of Building Information Modeling (BIM) technologies, the advancement of sustainable construction projects, and the integration of digital platforms. The research findings serve as a foundation for developing effective strategies in the field of development that will contribute to enhancing the growth and competitiveness of the construction industry.*

Keywords: *construction sector, development, developer services, economic growth, real estate market, digitalization of construction, innovations in construction.*

Introduction

Developer services play a crucial role in the advancement of the construction sector, acting as a connecting link for market participants, from investors to end consumers. Modern conditions, including the rapid growth of urbanization, increasing ecological demands, and the introduction of digital technologies, are creating new challenges and opportunities for development. These processes significantly influence changes in the design and implementation approaches of construction projects, highlighting the necessity to seek innovative solutions to meet the growing needs of society.

In the context of global changes, the importance of sustainable development is growing, which is expressed in the growing interest in "green" technologies, energy-efficient buildings and the creation of a comfortable urban environment. The modern real estate market is changing rapidly, and development services are at the center of these changes. The constantly growing needs of the population, the development of technologies and the changing legal framework create both new opportunities and serious challenges for developers. At the same time, the construction sector faces a number of problems, including a shortage of qualified personnel, difficulties in attracting investment, deficiencies in the regulatory framework, the need to introduce new technologies into traditional processes. In this article, we will consider the current problems facing the industry and assess the prospects for its development.

The purpose of this article is to study current trends, identify the main problems and determine the prospects for the development of services in the construction industry. Based on the analysis of the current state of the industry and best practices, a number of solutions are proposed that will help improve the efficiency of development activities and form sustainable development models.

Research methods and materials

To achieve the goals of this study, an integrated approach was used, including qualitative and quantitative methods of analysis. This allowed us to comprehensively study the development of services in the construction sector. The study is based on secondary sources and empirical observations, which ensures the reliability and impartiality of the findings.

One of the main research methods was the analysis of secondary data. This includes reports and statistical materials published by leading construction and development companies, government agencies and international organizations. This information provides information on current trends and problems in development activities, as well as short-term and long-term forecasts for the development of the field. In particular, materials from reports on the state of the construction industry, real estate market research, the introduction of innovative technologies and sustainable construction practices were used.

Content analysis was used to study and systematize existing publications on the topic of development, as well as news and trends in the construction sector. This method helped to identify key changes in approaches to developer services, as well as innovative practices that have become popular in recent years.

The study material included data from analytical reports, statistical data on the state of the construction market, materials from international and national conferences, as well as examples of successful development projects. Based on this information, recommendations were developed to improve the activities of developers in modern market conditions.

Research Results

The results of the analysis confirm that the construction sector of Uzbekistan is in a phase of active growth, but faces a number of challenges, including regional imbalances and a slowdown in the real estate market. Infrastructure development, digitalization and attracting investment remain the main factors determining the development of the industry in the coming years.

In January 2024, the volume of construction work in Uzbekistan increased by 24.5% compared to the same period in 2023. This indicates that the industry is developing significantly as a result of the active implementation of state programs in the field of infrastructure and housing construction. Priority is given to projects aimed at reducing the cost of housing and introducing innovative technologies.

In 2023, within the framework of the investment program, construction and reconstruction work was completed on 2,526 social and infrastructure facilities with a total cost of \$ 116 billion. In 2024, most of the investments will continue, including with the participation of foreign partners (Russia, China, Turkey, the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development).

The construction industry of Uzbekistan is showing steady growth. In January 2024, the volume of construction work amounted to 6.7 trillion soums (about 534 million dollars), which is 24.5 percent more than in January last year. These data indicate that the active development of the industry, which plays an important role in the country's economy, has resumed.

At the beginning of 2024, there were 34 thousand construction companies operating in Uzbekistan, 21.4 percent of which were located in Tashkent. The capital remains the leader in construction activity and investment attractiveness. Successful implementation of state reforms aimed at modernizing infrastructure, attracting investment and increasing economic growth is evidence of progress in this area.

In January-May 2024, objects worth 59.1 trillion soums were built in Uzbekistan. The following categories are distinguished in the composition of the completed works:

- Construction of buildings and structures: 40.4 trillion soums;
- Construction of civil facilities: 12.5 trillion soums;
- Specialized construction work: 6 trillion soums.

These figures indicate the rapid development of the construction sector of our country in the first half of the year.

Since the beginning of 2023, the volume of apartment sales on the real estate market of Uzbekistan has decreased by 5.7%. In Tashkent, the price of secondary housing fell to \$1,142 per square meter, and rental prices also showed a decline. [1]

According to the Center for Economic Research and Reforms, demand for housing declined in June after two months of growth. The largest decrease in the number of transactions was recorded in Syrdarya (-21%), Bukhara (-20%) and Andijan (-16%) regions. These changes reflect a slowdown in activity in the real estate market.

At the same time, it was noted that activity in Tashkent real estate market increased by almost 5%. According to the results of the first half of 2024, the largest decrease in the volume of transactions was observed in Navoi region (-26.5%), Tashkent region (-13.8%) and Jizzakh region (-10.6%).

However, positive changes are observed in a number of regions. The highest growth in activity was recorded in Andijan region (+12.7%), Khorezm region (+8.3%), Kashkadarya region (+6%), and the Republic of Karakalpakstan (+8.1%). These figures indicate that changes in the real estate market are not uniform due to regional characteristics and current economic factors [4].

Thus, the construction industry of Uzbekistan is attractive to foreign investors and continues to demonstrate positive development. Unlike Kazakhstan, where the construction market is mainly controlled by local companies, Uzbekistan is actively attracting foreign investment.[7]

The number of construction companies in the country is steadily increasing, especially in the construction of buildings and structures, including civil facilities. An important step was the introduction of 626 international standards for product quality and safety, which significantly improved the conditions for foreign developers and investors.

Tashkent maintains a leading position in the construction sector: large builders account for 19.7% of all construction companies and 27.8% of the volume of work. The largest investments and use of modern technologies are observed in the capital. [2]

Despite the rapid development of digitalization and the growth of construction volumes, Uzbekistan is still at the development stage. This requires large developers to carefully assess the risks before entering the market. Activity in the real estate sector is mainly supported by local companies, which emphasizes the importance of the domestic market in the development of the sector.

From July 1, 2024, all construction contracts will be transferred to a digital format. The procedures for accepting objects and financial transactions will be digitized through the Transparent Construction platform, which will reduce the risk of corruption and increase the efficiency of processes.

The study identified the main trends, problems and prospects for the development of services in the construction sector. Modern development companies are adapting to changing market conditions, including the growing demand for environmentally sustainable projects, the

introduction of digital technologies and increasing requirements for design quality. These factors stimulate the development of innovative solutions, such as the use of building information modeling (BIM) technologies, automation of design and management processes, and the integration of green standards. [5]

The use of information modeling technologies (BIM, Building Information Modeling) in development services radically changes traditional approaches to the design, construction and use of real estate. The use of BIM makes projects more attractive to investors due to their predictability and transparency. Information in the digital model allows for a detailed assessment of the self-healing capacity of the facility, possible risks and the number of resources required.[9]

In addition, BIM helps to create differentiated offers in the real estate market. The introduction of such technologies increases the competitiveness of developers by offering more modern and high-quality solutions to customers.

The analysis showed that the complexity of regulatory and legal regulation remains one of the main problems of the industry, which often lags behind the pace of technological development. This hinders the introduction of advanced methods, such as the use of renewable energy sources and recycled materials. In addition, the study identified a shortage of qualified specialists necessary for the implementation of modern development projects, and limited financing opportunities, especially for small and medium-sized companies.

The results of the study showed the need for an integrated approach to the development of services, including cooperation with the state, the introduction of educational programs to train a new generation of specialists, as well as the development of partnerships with market participants. These measures will contribute to increasing the efficiency of development activities and the sustainable development of the construction industry as a whole.

Analysis of the research results

Future predictions show that companies that can integrate innovative approaches into their activities will be the most successful. The introduction of hybrid financial models, cooperation with the state and participation in international initiatives can be effective tools for increasing business sustainability. [3]

The study confirmed that development services are of strategic importance in the development of the construction industry and the formation of a modern urban environment. They are a link between investors, designers, contractors and end users, integrating economic, social and environmental aspects into construction projects.

One of the main trends identified during the study was the greening of the industry. The increased interest in sustainable development is associated with the requirements of the international environmental agenda, as well as with the needs of consumers for energy-efficient and environmentally friendly objects. This confirms the need to actively introduce "green" standards, which can become a competitive advantage for developers.

Another important trend is digitalization, which encompasses the design, construction, and operation of facilities. The use of building information modeling (BIM), digital platforms, and the Internet of Things (IoT) technologies significantly increases the efficiency of projects, optimizes the costs and timing of their implementation. However, the full implementation of these technologies requires the development of a regulatory framework and a personnel training system. [8]

Problems such as insufficient funding, regulatory restrictions, and personnel shortages hinder the development of services. To solve them, an integrated approach is needed, including state-level incentive measures, attracting private investment, and creating educational programs to train a new generation of specialists.

The prospects for development activities are associated with the active development of "smart city" technologies, the implementation of integrated development projects, and the creation of multifunctional spaces. These areas allow taking into account the modern needs of the population, such as comfort, affordability and environmental safety, as well as responding to global problems such as climate and demographic changes.

Thus, the development of development services requires the synergy of innovative technologies, sustainable approaches and strategic management. This will increase the competitiveness of the construction industry, create conditions for the formation of a comfortable urban environment and the sustainable development of modern cities.

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